

D1.1. Project management Guidelines

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PROJECT INFORMATION

Project full title: Harmonised Life Cycle Assessment methods for sustainable and circular BIO based systems

Acronym: LCA4BIO

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-04 - Environmental sustainability and circularity criteria for industrial bio-based systems

Start date: 1st January 2024

Duration: 36 months

List of participants:

PARTNER N°	PARTICIPANT ORGANIZATION	ACRONYM
1 (Coord.)	CONTACTICA SL	CTA
2	AALBORG UNIVERSITET	AAU
3	LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	LIST
4	INSTITUT NATIONAL DES SCIENCES APPLIQUEES DE TOULOUSE	INSA TOULOUSE
5	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET	NTNU
6	BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE	B4C
7	BUSINESS E-INCUBATOR GO-UP	GOUP
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	CESEFOR
9	SONAE ARAUCO PORTUGAL SA	SONAE
10	ASOCIACION PARA LA CERTIFICACION ESPANOLA FORESTAL	PEFC ESPAÑA

DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Document Number:	D1.1
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WP:	WP1. Project Management.
Task:	T1.1. Project management procedures.
Author:	Contactica SL
Abstract:	This document covers the description of the project management structures and the procedures that the LCA4BIO project will follow to ensure appropriate project coordination (i.e., communication between partners and with the European Commission, monitoring the evolution of the actions and proceedings, monitoring of resources, quality assurance and knowledge management).

Version	Date	Description
Version 1	09/05/2024	First version

1 PROJECT MANAGEMENT STRUCTURES

1.1 Decision making bodies

1.1.1 Project Coordinator (PC)

The coordinator of LCA4BIO is CONTACTICA (CTA) being Manuel Román the Project Coordinator and Anahí Fernández the Project Manager of the project. They will be in charge of making all contacts with the European Commission and the only entitled interlocutors with the Project Officer. The PC will, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it, as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. In particular, the PC will be responsible for:

- Monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under the Grant Agreement.
- Keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available.
- Collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports and other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Funding Authority.
- Organise periodic project meetings, preparing meetings' agenda and chair the project meetings.
- Transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned.
- Administering the financial contribution of the Funding Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks.

1.1.2 General Assembly

The General Assembly consists of one representative of each partner. It is the executive body of LCA4BIO and will be in charge of the project monitoring, day-to-day coordination, and periodic reporting (including reviews), risks, trouble shooting, and applying fallback measures when necessary. It is also responsible for the quality assurance of project results and financial monitoring of the project including partners. The General Assembly will also prepare the periodic reports, guiding the partners in the administrative requirements.

The General Assembly will meet twice a year. Although it will be possible to call an extraordinary meeting in case of arising conflicts or any other trouble that could hinder the normal execution of the project.

The decision-making mechanism within the General Assembly will be by a majority of (2/3) of the votes. In case of tie right of vote, the coordinator (CTA) will hold the decisive vote.

If a partner is absent during voting, the partner can give in advance to the coordination a written authorization (via email) with their vote to a specific decision. In case of not sending this written authorization, they will lose the right to vote to that specific decision.

If a partner gives up the project once the project is running, the partner will lose the right of vote. If this partner is replaced, the vote will be given to the new partner. In case that the partner is not replaced, the decision-making mechanism will continue being the same.

A Member which can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of a Consortium Body may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision.

1.1.3 Steering Committee (SC)

The SC will be the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly. The SC will be composed by the Project Coordinator and the Work Packages Leaders. It will be responsible for:

- Discussion and assessment of the general project progress and project achievements in relation to the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Risk due diligence, troubleshooting, and validation and adoption of contingency plans if necessary.
- Quality assurance of project results and financial monitoring of the project including partners.
- To agree on modifications, including budget redistributions and task schedule variations.
- To monitor results to be protected and advising partners on the means of protection.

This body will meet at least quarterly when required by specific issues, preferably online. An extraordinary meeting will be also held online at any time upon request of any member of the Steering Committee.

1.1.4 Innovation & Exploitation Board (IEB)

The IEB will provide technical, legal and economic expertise in technology transfer, supporting guidance on IPR and innovation management, and commercial assessment to enable the transfer of project's results outside the consortium for exploitation purposes. CTA has a long experience in conducting effective exploitation. The IEB will be chaired by CTA and formed by at least one person for every partner with exploitable results. They will deal with the IP management following the IAPED strategy, project milestones monitoring, benchmarking, approval of dissemination materials, and risk due diligence on the implementation of the Exploitation Plan. The IEB will provide guidance to a multi-actor implementation and optimization of project activities, result transferability at industrial scale, and their exploitability to accelerate market access. As a first step, the IEB will approve the final reports, publications or any other type of dissemination material affecting the exploitation of the project results by simple majority.

1.1.5 WP Leaders (WPL)

WPL direct the day-to-day technical planning and work within the WP. The WPL coordinates, plans, monitors and reports to the PC about its WP progress (including budget issues). WPLs review, together with the PC, deliverables, milestones, risks and contingency plans related to their WP. The WPL will report regularly (at least once each 2 months by email) to the PC about the status of its WP.

WPL is the responsible of organizing monthly or bimonthly online WP-specific meetings where the rest of the partners involved in the WP will be also attending. Each partner will have 5-10 min to present their progress, deviations and next steps. The WPL will send to the PC the minutes of the meeting and the PPTs prepared by the partners. This shall include an additional slide detailing the next steps to be taken at WP level.

1.1.6 External Advisory Board (EAB)

The Advisory Board members will be external to LCA4BIO and independent from its partners. The EAB will support the Project Governance by participating in Project Meetings (at least once a year), in order to review scientific and technical results of the project and give advice towards further advancements to be achieved. To do so, first each member will sign an NDA.

Through knowledge transfer, the EAB will contribute to the maximization of the project impacts in terms of implementation, exploitation and dissemination. To do so, they will provide insights on further advancements needed to achieve the project objectives and accommodate them to the market and target group needs, in accordance with relevant policies.

1.2 Conflict resolution

To solve the problems that could compromise the success of the project, the following steps will be taken:

- 1) First, the problem will be discussed at the WP level and an attempt will be made to arrive at a solution.

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- 2) If the above is not enough, the problem will be discussed at the Steering Committee level and an attempt will be made to arrive at a solution.
- 3) If the above is not enough, the problem will be discussed at General Assembly level.
- 4) Ultimately, if none of the above is enough, the coordinator will discuss the problem with the European Commission and an attempt will be made to reach a solution.

2 PROJECT MANAGEMENT

2.1 Project documents

It is expected that over the course of LCA4BIO project many documents will be produced. It is, therefore, vital that document management processes are followed in order to enable users to locate and identify relevant files and to ensure version control.

2.1.1 Storage

The documents generated in LCA4BIO will be stored in the SharePoint created specifically for this project in Microsoft TEAMS. Also, WP-specific folders will be made available by WP leaders in order to share relevant information of each WP and to share living documents.

2.1.2 Document templates

Document templates are produced using a standard format including defined styles, page layout and content structure. These templates are prepared by CTA and will be available on the General folder of the project's SharePoint.

Templates have been produced for:

- Deliverables (MS Word format)
- Meeting Signatures (MS Word format)
- Meeting Minutes (MS Word format)
- Presentations (MS Powerpoint format)

For all project documents these templates must be used. These templates may be updated as the project progresses. Therefore, consortium partners must download the most up to date version from the Sharepoint.

2.1.3 Document coding

Each document will use a structured file name. This method of document coding produces a unique reference for all LCA4BIO documents stored on the website and LCA4BIO SharePoint.

Documents must be structured using the following. Minutes from meetings will include the date of the meeting (in the format YYYYMMDD):

LCA4BIO_WP [WP NUMBER]_[DOCUMENT TYPE AND REFERENCE]_v[VERSION NUMBER]_[STATUS(draft/final)]

One example of this coding is:

LCA4BIO_WP1_D1.1_v1_draft

3 COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION MANAGEMENT

3.1 Internal communication

All-important e-mails sent among partners shall be copied forwarded to Anahí Fernández and, also, Lucía García when the topic is related to the technical part, to keep them informed about the situation and the progress (or problems) of the project. **Besides, all e-mails among partners within a specific WP shall be copied and forwarded to the WP leader.**

3.2 Communication & Dissemination activities

3.2.1 Management of the disclosure of results

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 17.4 of the Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section Dissemination, subject to the following provisions.

This does not change the obligation to protect results as described in Annex 5 (section for Article 16) of the Grant Agreement, the confidentiality and security obligations in Article 13, or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 15 (see also section 4.4 of the Consortium Agreement), all of which still apply.

When a partner intends to disseminate its results through a scientific publication or presentation at an event (abstracts, poster, slides, articles), the partner must give advance notice to the others of (through the IEB once formed) — unless agreed otherwise — **at least 30 days before the publication**, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other partner may object within — unless agreed otherwise — **15 days** of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests.

3.2.2 Informing about the activities

When a partner plans to participate or organise a communication activity, the Communication team (consult project’s contact list) needs to be informed **at least one week** beforehand so this activity can be shared through social networks and other channels.

3.2.3 Monitoring the activities

When a partner carries out a communication or a dissemination activity, that partner must inform the communication team by email sending all the information available related to the activity, with pictures and other supportive documents when possible.

Every 3 months, the communication team will share with the partners and Excel file that compile all activities they are aware of. Partners are required to check and update if something is missing.

4 PROJECT MONITORING AND CONTROL

4.1 Meetings

Once a WP meeting is carried out, minutes of the main outcomes of it must be prepared and sent to the Project coordinator as well as the partners involved in the WP. It must also be uploaded to the SharePoint.

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4.2 Financial monitoring

The project coordinator will send an email informing of the execution of a payment. To avoid damages or inconveniences in case of error or fraud, within 3 days after the payment, the partners must confirm by mail the receipt of the payment.

4.3 Periodic reporting

The reporting period 1 (RP1) closes on M18 and RP2 closes on M36. Consequently, on M19 and M37 the PC is going to send the Technical Report template so every partner can complete it. Two weeks will be given to complete this task and send back a first draft. Any additional information required will be asked as well with specify due dates.

Besides, the PC will ask partners to send their Financial Statements to be checked before submitting them to the Participant Portal for each periodic reporting period.

4.4 Task frequency

4.4.1 Monthly - Bimonthly

The progress of the WPs will be evaluated and measured based upon achievements of Project Milestones and Deliverables, as well as project workflow. For this purpose, an email explaining the situation after each periodic WP meeting must be sent including the minutes and presentation materials. The set date for this sending is at maximum one week after each WP meeting.

4.4.2 Every 3 months

A Steering Committee meeting will be held every 3 months, with the possibility to postpone some in the case a date is not suitable. Work Package leaders will report on the WP progress and inform about any kind of risk, deviation or any other subject that need to be discussed among the partners.

4.4.3 Every six months

Meeting of the General Assembly. Meetings will be always organized at the location of a different partner's institute or at the location of the industrial partners. In general, hybrid meetings open to online attendance will be enabled.

Each partner will present the interim results and data achieved in the form of an oral presentation and in the form of electronic files containing all details. Review and assessment against the deliverables and milestones, and corrective measures of potential deviation in the Work Plan. Furthermore, the consortium will evaluate the feasibility of the project regarding scientific results and use of resources. The consortium will identify weak points and will adjust and improve the WPs accordingly.

The minutes of the meetings and all presentations and reports will be compiled by the coordinator and distributed among all partners.

4.4.4 Every 12 months

Assessment against the deliverables and milestones, and corrective measures of potential deviation in the Work Plan.

The milestones indicated for each work package, plus the mid-term and final reviews will be used to assess the progress of the project and the ability of the program to accomplish the tasks specified and to achieve the desired results. Any changes in the work plan that are suggested by these reviews – necessary for correction or remedial action - will be discussed by the General Assembly, and special review meetings will be held regarding the mid-term and final reviews to which a representative from the commission will be invited.

After every 12 months, the consortium will evaluate the feasibility of the project regarding scientific results and use

of resources. The EAB will be invited to this meeting to give advice related to the work done during the year. The consortium will identify weak points and will adjust and improve the WPs accordingly. The evaluation may be made in the presence of a representative of the EC.

The Commission will be invited to all the meetings and notified at least 6 weeks in advance and will be provided with the minutes within one month after the meeting.

5 FAILURE-MODE-EFFECTS ANALYSIS (FMEA) METHODOLOGY

The responsibility of the risk management plan is assumed by the Project Coordinator. For this aim, the FMEA (Failure Mode Effects Analysis) methods will be used. This will be applied to each Work Package and across the relations between Work Packages.

The Failure Mode Effects Analysis is a step-by-step approach used to predict, identify and mitigate the risks of the project. The steps that compose this method are the following:

- Identify the tasks that are going to be developed during the project and the objectives of them. In the FMEA approach, these tasks are called functions.
- For each function, guess the possible failures that may happen. It is important to be precise and return to define the functions if an inconsistency occurs.
- For each possible failure, it is necessary to determine the potential consequences. In this regard it is important to determine which Work Packages will be affected and how.
- Once the risk and the consequences have been determined it is important to classify them. In this project, three colours will be used to define the level of the risk: low (green), medium (yellow) and high (red). If the risk has several consequences, it will be characterized by the colour of the most severe one.
- For each risk it is important to establish the list of possible causes and install controls of the process that detect the failure or reduce its effects in case of happening.
- It is also crucial to define mitigating measurements to lower the severity of the risks.

The potential risks are established at the beginning of the project, based on the proposal. However, other risks and problems may appear during the development of the project. All of them will be analysed following the FMEA steps. This includes the characterization of the problem using the colour code established and the adoption of mitigating measurements in order to reduce the harmful effects of the problem.

The final step of the risk management plan is to document as problems arise to have a registration of all the incidents that took place, the mitigation measurements adopted and the consequences of the problems.

The risk management plan will be discussed and updated during the General Assembly meetings.

6 RISK MANAGEMENT

6.1 Monitoring

It is the responsibility of all partners to update the coordinator about the status of each risk and the effectiveness of the mitigation plan in order to update the risk management register.

Each partner is responsible for executing risk mitigation measures related to the task that they lead. If a mitigation action cannot be effectively carried out or does not solve the risk, the coordinator must be informed as soon as possible. Consequently, the mitigation measure will be modified in a more efficient way.

Risks will be collected in a "Risk Register" that will be checked in every personal meeting. The Risk Register contains a number of columns under which each risk is analysed individually. The Risk Register has been created in Excel,

which allows the order and grouping of the risks according to the information in any of the columns. This register will be stored in the project's Sharepoint, so all partners have access to it.

6.2 Reporting new risks

In addition to the risks and mitigation/corrective actions identified at the proposal stage, subsequent risks further identified by each partner during the course of the project should be reported by filling up a risk registration template, sending it to the coordinator.

The template (Annex: **risk registration form**) will enable LCA4BIO partners to report risks as they arise or where there is an increased chance of a risk materializing.

ANNEX 1. RISK REGISTRATION FORM

RISK REGISTRATION FORM

- Person that detected the risk:
- Organization:

Reporting Period	RP1/ RP2
Date registered	
Description of the risk	
WPs involved	
Type of risk	<p><i>The following types have been identified:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gen: General risk • Tech: Technical risk • Man: Management risk • Expl: Exploitation (commercial) risk • Ethics: Ethical risks, including privacy legal concerns
Risk impact	<p><i>What would be the impact on the project if the risk event happened.</i></p>
Likelihood of occurrence*	<p><i>Provides an assessment on how likely it is that this risk will occur. Examples are: L-Low (, M-Medium (31-70%), H-High (>70%).</i></p>
Severity of effect*	<p><i>Provides an assessment of the impact that the occurrence of this risk would have on the project.</i></p>
Grade of risk*	<p><i>Likelihood x Severity</i></p>
Mitigation measure	
Owner/responsible	

*a guide to calculate these factors is below.

ANNEX 2. GUIDE TO CALCULATE THE GRADE OF THE RISK

Rating for Likelihood and Seriousness for each risk						
L	Rated as Low	E	Rated as Extreme (Used for Seriousness only)			
M	Rated as Medium	NA	Not Assessed			
H	Rated as High					
Grade: Combined effect of Likelihood/Seriousness						
		Severity				
		Trivial	Low	Moderate	High	Extreme
Likelihood	Rare	VL	L	L	M	M
	Unlikely	L	L	M	M	M
	Moderate	L	M	M	M	H
	Likely	M	M	M	H	H
	Very likely	M	M	H	H	E
Recommended actions for grades of risk						
Grade	Risk mitigation actions					
E	Mitigation actions, to reduce the likelihood and seriousness, to be identified and implemented as soon as the project commences as a priority.					
H	Mitigation actions, to reduce the likelihood and seriousness, to be identified and appropriate actions implemented during project execution.					
M	Mitigation actions, to reduce the likelihood and seriousness, to be identified and costed for possible action if funds permit.					
L	To be noted - no action is needed unless grading increases over time.					
VL	To be noted - no action is needed unless grading increases over time.					